

PERFORMANCES OF Y_2SiO_5 COATING SYSTEM FOR CARBON/CARBON COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: As an oxidation protection system for carbon/carbon composites beyond 1800K, authors have proposed Y_2SiO_5 coating system, which is a multilayer coating system composed of a outer Y_2SiO_5 layer and a inner SiC layer. This work evaluated the Y_2SiO_5 coating in re-entry condition, which some space crafts will meet in re-entry. First, erosion test was executed in low oxygen pressure and high velocity gas flow(Mach 3, Ar-20vol% O_2) by arc wind tunnel. The Y_2SiO_5 coating protected a carbon substrate from the erosion test at 2073K for 50 minutes, and the SiC layer was oxidized in active. The Y_2SiO_5 layer as erosion-tested had adhered to the SiC layer. Next, isothermal oxidation tests were executed in Ar-0.2vol% O_2 with an electric furnace. The Y_2SiO_5 coating performs oxidation protection at 1973K for more than 10 hours, but, adhesion of Y_2SiO_5 /SiC interface was degraded. This work shows that the Y_2SiO_5 coating performs oxidation protection above 1973K.

KEYWORDS: yttrium silicate, carbon/carbon composites, oxidation protection, silicon carbide, yttrium silicide, plasma spraying, arc wind tunnel, active oxidation.

INTRODUCTION

Carbon/Carbon(C/C) composite is a desirable structural material for use in aerospace application at elevated temperature[1-3]. Many efforts have been made to develop effective oxidation protection systems for C/C composites[4-12]. SiC coating system is one of the most effective oxidation protection systems up to about 1800K[13]. Beyond 1800K, SiC coating is rapidly lost in low oxygen pressure by active oxidation as re-entry, which some space crafts meet. Active oxidation of SiC is expressed as Eqn 1.

For temperature beyond 1800K, authors have proposed Y_2SiO_5 oxidation protection coating system[14-16], which is a multilayer coating system composed of a outer Y_2SiO_5 layer and a inner SiC layer, as shown in Fig.1.

Fig. 1: Schematic illustration of Y_2SiO_5 coating

The Y_2SiO_5 layer is one of the best oxygen barriers in oxides[15]. The SiC layer is an interlayer to adhere between the Y_2SiO_5 layer and C/C composite, and a reaction barrier between the Y_2SiO_5 layer and C/C composite. YSi_x , which is a metallic compound composed of Y, Si, C and a few O, is an effective material to adhere the Y_2SiO_5 layer to the SiC layer with chemical bonding. Therefore, the YSi_x/SiC layer, which is composed of YSi_x and SiC, is inserted between the Y_2SiO_5 layer and the SiC layer[16]. Our program to develop the Y_2SiO_5 coating has accomplished to form YSi_x/SiC layer on CVD-SiC layer, and to form Y_2SiO_5 layer with gas tightness of our target, which is below $2.0 \times 10^{-14} m^2 s^{-1} Pa^{-1}$ in gas permeability. This work evaluated the Y_2SiO_5 coating in two conditions as re-entry.

EXPERIMENT

Erosion Test

An erosion test was executed with an erosion testing machine of Japan Ultra-high-Temperature Materials Research Center, as shown in Fig.2[17]. This machine is a kind of arc heating tunnel, and generates high temperature and high speed gas flow in the center of a vacuum chamber, and is used for evaluating durability of materials applied for high temperature gas passage parts. A specimen was moved into high temperature and high speed gas flow after generating the gas flow.

A Y_2SiO_5 coated graphite was prepared for a erosion test as follow. A YSi_x/SiC layer was formed on one face of a SiC coated graphite[16], and a Y_2SiO_5 layer was coated on the YSi_x/SiC layer by atmospheric plasma spraying. The Y_2SiO_5 layer was about $150\mu m$ thick. Then the Y_2SiO_5 coated graphite heated for adhesion between the Y_2SiO_5 layer and the YSi_x/SiC layer at 1873K for 1 hour in Ar of $1 \times 10^5 Pa$. For gas tightening of the Y_2SiO_5 layer, the Y_2SiO_5 coated graphite was splayed with slurry of YSiBZ1122, which was a oxide of $Y_2O_3:SiO_2:B_2O_3:ZnO = 1:1:2:2$ in molar ratio, and it was heated at 1773K for 10 hours in Ar. YSi_x of the YSi_x/SiC layer is oxidized to be Y_2SiO_5 by the gas tightening process. The SiC coated graphite was $50mm \times 30mm \times 3mm$ in dimension, and was covered with CVD-SiC layers of $150\mu m$ thickness on all the faces. Gas tightness(gas permeability) of the Y_2SiO_5 layer is shown in Table 1.

Conditions of the erosion test are as follow. The surface temperature of the specimen was 2073K, and the total holding time was 50 minutes. The flowing gas was 80vol% N_2 -20vol% O_2 , and the velocity of the gas flow was about Mach 3. The gas flow rate was $8.3 \times 10^{-4} m^3/s$ at 293K. The nozzle blowing the gas was 100mm in diameter, and the specimen was set 40mm apart from a nozzle. The operation time of the erosion test machine is limited less than 30

Fig.2 A schematic illustration of a gas erosion testing machine[17]

minutes. Therefore, two operation were executed for the erosion test for 50minutes. Pressure of the vacuum chamber was $6.7 \times 10 \text{ Pa}$. The surface temperature of the specimen was measured with a radiation ratio thermometry, and the back surface temperature was measured with a narrow band thermometry.

Table 1 Specimens and heating condition.

Test	Substrate	Gas tightness of Y_2SiO_5 layer $\text{m}^2\text{s}^{-1}\text{Pa}^{-1}$	Heating condition
Erosion test	Graphite	1.0×10^{-14}	2073K - 50m
Isothermal oxidation test	C/C composite	1.0×10^{-15}	1973K - 10h
	Graphite	1.0×10^{-14}	2073K - 1h

Isothermal Oxidation Test

Isothermal oxidation tests were executed to evaluate Y_2SiO_5 coating in a static heating condition, which was in low oxygen pressure without a high speed gas flow. A Y_2SiO_5 coated C/C composite and Y_2SiO_5 coated graphite were prepared for the isothermal oxidation test as same as the erosion test. A SiC coated C/C composite was used for the specimen preparation, and had a conversion SiC layer and a CVD-SiC layer on all the faces, and was 50mm x 30mm x 2mm in dimension. The CVD-SiC layer was about $100 \mu\text{m}$ thick. The gas tightness of the Y_2SiO_5 layers is shown in Table 1. The C/C composite substrate was made out of 2-D PAN-type carbon fiber fabrics.

An Iridium-heater electric furnace was used for the test, and the effective heating area of the furnace was 30mm x 15mm. The Y_2SiO_5 coated C/C composite was tested at 1973K for 10h, and the Y_2SiO_5 coated graphite was tested at 2073K for 1h. A SiC coated C/C composite was tested as a reference by the isothermal oxidation test at 1973K. Atmosphere of the isothermal test was controlled by gas flow, rate of which was about $3.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$. Ar-0.2vol% O_2 gas was flowing while the test temperature was holding, and Ar gas was flowing while the temperature was elevating decreasing. The temperature of a specimen was measured with a narrow band thermometry, which was corrected with a W-5%Re thermocouple.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Erosion Test

A Y_2SiO_5 coated graphite as fabricated has a Y_2SiO_5 layer, a YSi_x/SiC layer and a CVD-SiC

Fig.3 Cross-section microstructure of a Y_2SiO_5 coated graphite as fabricated

Fig.4 An appearance of the erosion test.

layer as shown in Fig.3. As to the Y_2SiO_5 layer, a gas-tight plasma sprayed Y_2SiO_5 layer with about $150\ \mu m$ thickness is covered by a porous Y_2SiO_5 layer with about $30\ \mu m$ thickness. The porous Y_2SiO_5 layer was formed as a residue of YSiBZ1122 by gas tightening of plasma-sprayed Y_2SiO_5 layer. As far as interfacial microstructures between the Y_2SiO_5 layer and the YSi_x/SiC layer is observed, the Y_2SiO_5 layer has good adhesion to the YSi_x/SiC layer, as shown in Fig.3.

Fig.4 is an appearance of the gas erosion test, which shows that the specimen is held with a zirconia-coated graphite tool.

In the erosion test, the surface temperature of the specimen was kept from 2073K to 2123K. The specimen was heated beyond 2073K for 23 minutes at the first operation, and 27 minutes at the second operation. After the test, the Y_2SiO_5 coating had no catastrophic damage such as appearance of the inner CVD-SiC layer and debonding of the Y_2SiO_5 layer, as shown in Fig.5. Fig.6 shows that the erosion test oxidizes SiC of the YSi_x/SiC layer in active oxidation. SiC of YSi_x/SiC layer is lost at least about $20\ \mu m$ thickness, since the YSi_x/SiC layer in the center of the specimen is lost more than that of the edge part, which is 20mm apart from the center. Fig.6 also shows there are pores with a diameter of about $20\ \mu m$ in the Y_2SiO_5 layer as tested. The pores tends to expand in a direction from Y_2SiO_5/SiC interface to the surface of the Y_2SiO_5 layer. The Y_2SiO_5 layer adheres to the SiC layer after the erosion test. A graphite substrate of the specimen has no damage by the test. Consequently, the Y_2SiO_5 coating performs oxidation protection at 2073K for more than 50 minutes.

The back surface of the specimen was covered only with a CVD-SiC layer of about $150\ \mu m$.

Fig.5 Appearances of a Y_2SiO_5 coated graphite as fabricated and as erosion-tested at 2073K for 50min.

Fig.6 Cross-sections of aY_2SiO_5 coated graphite as erosion-tested at 2073K for 50min. Center of the specimen and 20mm from center.

After the erosion test for 50 minutes, a graphite substrate was appeared in the center of the back surface. Namely, the CVD-SiC layer of the back surface was lost by active oxidation. Back surface temperature was about 1753K with a narrow band thermometry.

Isothermal Oxidation Test

In the isothermal oxidation test of the SiC coated graphite at 1973K for 1h, a CVD-SiC layer was lost by active oxidation. The loss rate of the CVD-SiC layer was 17nm/s. These results shows that the isothermal oxidation test is executed in active oxidation for SiC.

After an isothermal oxidation test at 1973K for 10h, a Y_2SiO_5 coated C/C composite is gray in effective heating area, as shown in Fig.7. This gray color is due to IrO_2 vapor deposition

Fig.7 Appearances of a Y_2SiO_5 coated C/C coated C/C composite as fabricated and as tested in isothermal oxidation at 1973K for 10h.

Fig.8 Cross-sections of a Y_2SiO_5 coated C/C coated C/C composite as fabricated and as tested in isothermal oxidation at 1973K for 10h.

from Iridium-heater. Fig.7 also shows that the Y_2SiO_5 coating after the test has visible cracks on the surface. The Y_2SiO_5 layer as tested increases in thickness, as shown in Fig.8, since closed pores of the Y_2SiO_5 layer increases in number. Fig.8 also shows the CVD-SiC layer of the Y_2SiO_5 coating as tested is lost, since the Y_2SiO_5 layer is just on the conversion-SiC layer. The conversion-SiC layer is characterized by fiber patterns, because the conversion-SiC layer is made by siliconizing a C/C composite. The loss of the CVD-SiC layer is found to be about 60 μ m in thickness by observing the Y_2SiO_5 coating out of the effective heating area. SiO_2 and $Y_2Si_2O_7$, which are products of passive oxidation of the CVD-SiC, were not observed in the Y_2SiO_5 coating as tested. This result shows that the CVD-SiC is lost by active oxidation. Adhesion between the Y_2SiO_5 layer and the YSi_x/SiC layer is degraded by the test, as shown in Fig.8.

Fig.9 A Y_2SiO_5 coated graphite as tested in isothermal oxidation at 2073K for 1h.

A Y_2SiO_5 coated graphite as tested in isothermal oxidation at 2073K for 1h has a gap in the Y_2SiO_5 layer, as shown in Fig.9. The gap is along the interface between the Y_2SiO_5 layer and the YSi_x/SiC layer, but the Y_2SiO_5 layer is not debonded. Fig.9 also shows that a graphite substrate has no oxidation damage.

Consequently, in the isothermal oxidation tests, the Y_2SiO_5 coating performs oxidation protection at 1973K for more than 10 hours, and at 2073K for more than 1 hour. The CVD-SiC layer was oxidized in active oxidation. But, adhesion of Y_2SiO_5/SiC interface was degraded by the isothermal oxidation tests.

DISCUSSION

Change of Y_2SiO_5 Layers in Isothermal Oxidation Test

Loss rate of SiC in active oxidation

In the isothermal oxidation test at 1973K for 10h, oxygen permeation in the Y_2SiO_5 layer depends mainly on solid state diffusion, since gas tightness of the Y_2SiO_5 layer is $1.0 \times 10^{-15} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$, and oxygen permeability constant of Y_2SiO_5 at 1973K is about $2 \times 10^{-10} \text{ kg s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-1}$ [16]. The oxygen permeation rate of the Y_2SiO_5 layer of 150 μ m is calculated to be $3 \times 10^{-8} \text{ kg s}^{-1} \text{ m}^{-2}$ at 1973K, which is about $4.5 \times 10^{-2} \mu\text{m/h}$ in active oxidation loss rate of SiC. On the other hand, the loss rate of the CVD-SiC layer of Y_2SiO_5 coating is 6 μ m/h at 1973K. Namely, the loss rate of SiC is measured to be 130 times as high as expected. There are two reasons for this high loss rate. One of the reasons is considered that oxygen diffusion coefficient in Y_2SiO_5 is increased by low oxygen potential, which due to joining Y_2SiO_5 to SiC. The other of the reasons is considered that the gas tightness of the Y_2SiO_5 layer is degraded by heating. For gas tightness, Y_2SiO_5 layers may be repaired by gas tightening treatment using YSiBZ1122.

Atomic movements in the Y_2SiO_5 coating

In oxygen movements in Y_2SiO_5 layers from the atmosphere to inner SiC, oxygen atoms or ions can move by solid state diffusion, and oxygen gas molecules can also move by gaseous diffusion, as shown in Fig.10. When oxygen reaches from the atmosphere to SiC, the oxygen

Fig.10 Atomic movements in a Y_2SiO_5 coating.

reacts with SiC, and SiO gas and CO gas are produced by the reaction. SiO gas and CO gas can be resolved into atoms or ions, and the atoms and ions can move to the atmosphere by solid state diffusion. SiO gas molecules and CO gas molecules can also move by gaseous diffusion. When amount of oxygen moved to SiC by solid state diffusion is equal to amount of oxygen in product gases moved by solid state diffusion, oxygen does not move in appearance, and interfacial microstructures are stable.

Adhesion of Y_2SiO_5 layers

Interface between Y_2SiO_5 and SiC is chemically stable at 2073K in Ar gas when the product gases can not escape as gas molecular from the interface between Y_2SiO_5 and SiC[16]. Heating the Y_2SiO_5 coating does not lead the Y_2SiO_5 layers to degradation in adhesion. On the other hand, active oxidation of SiC can degrade adhesion of the Y_2SiO_5 layers. When the product gases move to the atmosphere by gaseous diffusion, the interface is not stable. Namely, when the product gases is formed as gas molecular at the interface, the interface is loaded with pressure of the product gases. The gas pressure can form pores in Y_2SiO_5 , and can expand the pores at 1973K. The interface is, therefore, degraded in adhesion by the product gases.

Oxidation Protection by Y_2SiO_5 Coating System

Y_2SiO_5 coating system protects carbon substrates by active oxidation of an inner SiC layer. The loss rate of the inner SiC layer depends on the Y_2SiO_5 , since oxygen permeate through the Y_2SiO_5 layer. When the Y_2SiO_5 layer is perfectly debonded off, the SiC layer is rapidly lost. When all of the SiC layer is lost, oxidation of a carbon substrate starts. Life time of the Y_2SiO_5 coating depends on thickness of the SiC layer.

In the erosion test at 2073K for 50 minutes, SiC of the YSi_x/SiC layer of the specimen as tested is lost about 20 μ m thickness, but most of the CVD-SiC layer remains, as shown in Fig.9. The life time of the Y_2SiO_5 coating is much more than 50 minutes, and is estimated to be from 3h to 5h without the Y_2SiO_5 layer debonding.

In the isothermal test at 1973K, the life time of the Y_2SiO_5 coating of the Y_2SiO_5 coated C/C composite is estimated to be more than 10h without the debonding, since the conversion-SiC layer remaining is not enough to protect the C/C composite at 1973K. In the isothermal test at 2073K, the life time of the Y_2SiO_5 coating is more than 1h.

CONCLUSIONS

Beyond 1800K, Y_2SiO_5 oxidation protection coating system for C/C composites has been proposed. This work evaluated the Y_2SiO_5 coating in the gas erosion test and the isothermal oxidation test. Consequently, the Y_2SiO_5 coating performs oxidation protection at 1973K for more than 10h, and at 2073K for more than 1 hour in low oxygen pressure. The Y_2SiO_5 coating should be researched and developed much more to apply aerospace applications at elevated temperature.

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